

Data Compression Using Wavelet Transforms and Vector Quantization

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Abstract-- In this paper a general purpose compression coding algorithm is described, applicable to both sound and image data. Using recent developments in Discrete Wavelet Transforms (DWT) and Vector Quantization (VQ) the algorithm is compared to Direct Vector Quantization (DVQT) methods. Test results show a 19% to 84% improvement in SNR over DVQT for speech data and a 17% to 50% improvement in SNR for image data.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data and image compression are topics of current interest, particularly as a result of the developments in high speed data networks. Considerable research has been conducted into new algorithms for the efficient coding of image data using DCT, Vector Quantization and Sub-band coding methods [5,8]. Other areas being explored are fractal and wavelet based transformations [1].

This paper details a general purpose compression algorithm suitable for use on signal and image data using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Vector Quantization (VQ). Our algorithm uses the wavelet decomposition to form octal sub-bands which are individually encoded using vector quantization. A brief review of wavelet theory and the principles of vector quantization are presented followed by a synopsis of our results on speech and image data.

II. WAVELET THEORY

Much has been written recently on the subject of wavelet transforms and their applications to signal processing [1, 2]. The wavelet transform can be viewed as an alternate to the classical short time Fourier transform (STFT) in that it has a constant time-bandwidth product or constant Q factor. This allows for a longer time window to be used for filtering in the low frequency ranges and shorter time window for filtering in the high frequency ranges. This method gives better frequency resolution at lower frequencies and better time resolution at higher frequencies. By scaling and dilating the wavelet prototype function $\psi(t)$ appropriately, an octal division of the frequency scale may be effected. Typically a dilation factor of two is used for this dyadic scaling.

In order to form a multi-resolution decomposition of a signal $x(t)$ we introduce a scaling function $\phi(t)$ similar in form to the wavelet prototype $y(t)$. It is helpful at this point to view the scaling function as a lowpass filter and the wavelet function as a highpass filter.

For applications involving digital filtering it is necessary to discretize the wavelet transform resulting in the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). From the prototype functions we can define the discretized scaling and wavelet functions defined as [3]:

$$\psi(t)=2\sum_n h(n)\psi(2t-n) \quad \phi(t)=2\sum_n g(n)\phi(2t-n) \quad (1)$$

where $g(n)$ and $h(n)$ are highpass and lowpass filters respectively. The filter $g(n)$ may be obtained from:

$$g(n)=(-1)^n h(1-n) \quad (2)$$

A. One Dimensional DWT

For a one dimensional signal $x(n)$ we form the first decomposition level by convolving the sequence with the wavelet filter $g(n)$ and the scaling filter $h(n)$. The result of the convolution with $g(n)$ gives us a set of wavelet coefficients $d(n)$ while the convolution with $h(n)$ gives us the approximation coefficients $x'(n)$. Because of the redundancy of information we subsample each set of coefficients by two and normalize by a factor $\sqrt{2}$. The approximation coefficients $x'(n)$ are then convolved again with the filters $g(n)$ and $h(n)$ to form the next level of decomposition. This procedure is applied iteratively to each successive $x_m(n)$ to form $d_{m+1}(n)$ and $x_{m+1}(n)$. Ultimately we are left with M sets of wavelet coefficients denoted $\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_M\}$ and a residual approximation x_M . In general the convolution and subsampling is carried out by creating filter bank matrices of appropriate dimension and multiplying them by the input vector X_m . The following relationships are provided where G and H denote the filterbanks of $g(n)$ and $h(n)$ respectively [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{m+1} &= \sqrt{2} H X_m & d_{m+1} &= \sqrt{2} G X_m \\ 2H H^T &= I & 2G G^T &= I & H G^T &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Reconstruction of the original sequence can be viewed as successive reconstructions of each level starting from the lowest level M . We denote the reconstructed approximation and wavelet coefficients as X_{r_m} and d_{r_m} respectively. The following relationships are utilized in the synthesis process:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{r_m} &= 2H H^T X_m & d_{r_m} &= 2G^T G d_m \\ X_{m-1} &= X_{r_m} + d_{r_m} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

B. Two Dimensional DWT

The wavelet and scaling filter decomposition method is readily extended to the two dimensional case where the filters are separable. The filters are applied horizontally and vertically (i.e. by row and column). We denote the scaling and wavelet functions as :

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(t_1, t_2) &= \phi(t_1)\phi(t_2) \\ \Psi^1(t_1, t_2) &= \phi(t_1)\psi(t_2) \\ \Psi^2(t_1, t_2) &= \psi(t_1)\phi(t_2) \\ \Psi^3(t_1, t_2) &= \psi(t_1)\psi(t_2)\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

The same method of filter bank matrices as in the 1-dimensional case may be used here. The horizontal and vertical filters use the same prototype functions but may differ in size. Again the decomposition is applied iteratively which yields four sets of coefficients: $x_m(n1, n2)$ vertical lowpass and horizontal lowpass; $d_m^1(n1, n2)$ vertical lowpass and horizontal highpass; $d_m^2(n1, n2)$ vertical highpass and horizontal lowpass; $d_m^3(n1, n2)$ vertical highpass and horizontal highpass. Reconstruction of the two dimensional data is carried out in a similar manner to the one dimensional case [9].

C. Biorthogonal Wavelets

Because of the desire to use filters of linear phase in image analysis, we are forced to relax the orthogonality requirements of the basis functions. This results in a class of functions denoted as biorthogonal bases. When used in the wavelet decomposition algorithm we find that the analysis and synthesis filters are of different form. Letting H_0 and G_0 denote the analysis filters and H_1 and G_1 denote the synthesis filters, perfect image reconstruction may be obtained provided the following relations hold [4]:

$$H_0G_1=H_1G_0=0 \quad 2H_0H_1=2G_0G_1=I. \quad (6)$$

III. Vector Quantization:

Vector Quantization (VQ) can be viewed as a generalization of scalar quantization where a discrete level value is used to represent a range of continuous values. In the case of the vector quantizer a vector quantity is used to represent a range of vectors which fall within some predetermined distance measure. In view of Shannon's rate distortion theorem VQ will always outperform scalar quantization and will in fact approach the rate distortion limit if sufficiently large dimensions are used [6,8]. In our work we have found that bit rates of less than one bit per sample are achievable using vector quantization.

A. Design of Optimum Quantizer

Design of the optimum vector quantizer consists of an encoder, a decoder and a shared code book. The quantizer performs a mapping of an Nth order vector x onto another Nth order vector y illustrated by $y=q(x)$. The number of

vectors in the Y subspace is finite and may be viewed as a collection of cells. All x vectors falling within a prescribed distance of the centroid of a cell are mapped to that cell. The distance criterion is chosen to minimize the mean square error. The number of vectors (cells) in Y, denoted y_i , determine the code book size L. The rate of the quantizer is given by $R=\log_2(L)$ bits per vector, while $r=R/N$ gives the bits per pixel for the image data. The size of the cells is varied. The division of the Y space into cells is image dependent and requires the use of a training algorithm to determine bit allocation and cell size strategies. For this project the generalized Lloyd algorithm (GL or LBG [8]) was used. An initial code book is selected with L random cells assigned. A mapping of vectors is then iterated where the distance from the centroid of each cell is measured. If a cell is empty (less than three vectors assigned) it is incorporated into another adjacent cell while a more densely occupied cell is split. This continues until a stopping criteria is met. In this case that criteria was the difference in MSE measured between the iterations falling below a preset threshold [9].

IV. Speech and Data Coding

The general method of coding used here is known as analysis-synthesis coding and is commonly found in sub-band coding applications. The analysis of data is accomplished via the wavelet decomposition while the coding of the coefficients is achieved by vector quantization. Each coefficient level has its own code book assigned. Each level's code book in turn is allocated so many bits for representation based entirely on the energy content of the level. Levels of high energy content have more bits assigned and thus larger code books. This method of coding is contrasted with direct vector quantization where no decomposition takes place. For speech data compression a four level decomposition scheme was used resulting in five sets of coefficients: $\{x_4, d_4, d_3, d_2, d_1\}$. The energy level of each set of coefficients was then computed. Bit assignments to each level's code books were based on these energy levels.

A. Optimum Bit Allocation

Assignment of bits to each level's code books determined the size of the code book. Assignment was done on a quota system. If the normalized energy $E(d_m)$ of a level fell below a predetermined threshold, no bits were assigned thus allowing more bits to be assigned to higher energy levels. Once the desired level coefficients were selected based on $E(d_m)$, the actual bits assigned to the level were made based on the variance of the level itself. If we let B denote the desired average number of bits per vector and σ_m^2 the variance of level m, then the optimal bit allocation is given by:

$$b_m = \frac{B + \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{\sigma_m^2}{\rho^2}}{W_m} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\rho^2 = \left(\prod_{m=1}^k \sigma_m^2 \right)^{1/k}$$

is the geometric mean of the variances and W_m is the ratio between the number of coefficients at resolution level m and the number of coefficients in the original image or L_m/L_0 .

For speech data experimental results showed a concentration of energy in levels d_3 and d_4 . Using a threshold of $E(d_m) = .06$ allowed us to discard levels d_1 and d_4 replacing them with zeros. One problem encountered at this stage was the reduced number of training sets used to train the code books at the lower resolution levels. This problem was overcome by shifting data samples at the previous level $m-1$ and performing the wavelet decomposition again. This second set of vectors was then used to double the training vectors used for the code book of level m . Note that the sizes of the code books were dictated by the bit allocation algorithm. Each code book was then stored and reconstruction was done by looking up the appropriate code books in the decoder. Discarded coefficients in low energy levels were simply replaced by zero vectors of appropriate length in the decoding stage.

B Results

Tests were conducted on speech data with excellent results. Two data sets were used in the experiment. The first was used as training data for code book generation and consisted of 104100 samples of speech from three speakers sampled at 8 KHz. The second data set was used for testing and consisted of 20330 samples from an independent speaker not used in the training set. As a comparison direct vector quantization was used and the resulting SNR values compared. In this case we define SNR as:

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{E(x^2)}{D} \quad (8)$$

where $E(x^2)$ is the signal power and D is the mean square error between the original and reconstructed signals. Results showed a considerable increase in performance of Wavelet Transform Coding (WTC) over DVQT as the bit rate increased typically on the order of 19% to 55%. In direct comparison, for bit rates of .18 bps WTC resulted in an SNR of 3.0 dB while DVQT had an SNR of 2.5 dB, and for bit rates of 1.0 bps WTC had an SNR of 9.56 dB compared to 6.2 dB for DVQT. In all cases the WTC algorithm resulted in intelligible speech data of acceptable quality. Tests were also performed on transient signal coding with the WTC algorithm giving much better results over DVQT (Figures 1 and 2). This can easily be

explained as the WTC is able to extract transient information in the non-stationary signal whereas the DVQT is unable to provide sufficient code vectors to represent the changing structure of the signal. In the extreme case an 84% performance increase was noted for the WTC algorithm over DVQT for the transient signal case.

V. Image Data Coding

In this section we extend the one dimensional transform to the two dimensional case using the theory previously developed. Based on experimental results a three level decomposition scheme was adopted using the biorthogonal seventh order wavelet coefficients. As mentioned earlier the linear phase characteristics and exact reconstruction provided by the biorthogonal wavelets necessitated that different analysis and synthesis filters be used. The choice of the three level decomposition was arrived at by comparing the variances of the residual (x) coefficients at lower resolution levels. These lower levels were found to have increasingly large variances as the correlations between coefficients decreased. A total of ten coefficients $\{x_3, d_{11}, d_{12}, d_{13}, d_{21}, d_{22}, d_{23}, d_{31}, d_{32}, d_{33}\}$ were encoded after decomposition.

A. Optimum Bit Allocation

After decomposing the original image into the 10 coefficient sets an energy measure was made to determine net information content by level. We found that the residual set x_3 had the highest energy level with all other sets being much smaller. A problem was encountered when we tried using the bit allocation strategy of the one dimensional case; all bits were allocated to x_3 with none left for the other sets. By discarding all other coefficient sets all the high frequency information and thus edges are lost in the reconstruction. The solution used was to allocate a fixed number of bits to x_3 and divide the remainder within the other coefficients sets. Based on net energy content sets d_{11}, d_{21}, d_{31} and d_{32} were set to zero (no bits allocated). Eleven bits were set aside for x_3 and a value of $B=1$ was used for the allocation routine for sets $d_{12}, d_{22}, d_{13}, d_{23}$ and d_{33} .

The generalized Lloyd Algorithm used in the one dimensional case was used in the two dimensional case as well. Again we were presented with fewer training sets for lower resolution levels which we solved by shifting the previous level one sample horizontally and decomposing it resulting in double the training data.

B. Results

Tests were conducted by using two data sets. The first was a collage of 4 images used as a code book training set, the second was a 512 by 512, 256 shade image of Lenna. The Lenna image was not used in the training set. Comparisons with the DVQ algorithm were based on a Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) defined as:

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{D} \right) \quad (9)$$

where

$$D = d(x, y) = \frac{1}{N^2} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{l=1}^N (x_{kl} - y_{kl})^2$$

Tests results for a bit rate of .25 bpp (32:1 compression) resulted in a PSNR =27.37 dB for the WTC algorithm versus 20.7 dB for the DVQ method. The WTC coded image was degraded by jagged diagonal lines and blurring as a result of the smoothing effect of the wavelet filters. Using smaller size code vectors for a bit rate of .5 bpp raised the SNR to 29.5 dB with near perfect visual reconstruction (Figures 3, 4).

VI. Conclusions

In this paper we have successfully combined the multiresolution capabilities of the discrete wavelet transform with the compression capabilities of vector quantization to achieve better compression performance. Our methods have resulted in better Signal to Noise Ratios for a given bit rate when compared to direct vector quantization. At this time we are continuing to research the use of wavelet decomposition combined with other traditional compression techniques.

Figure 1. The original Transient Signal

Figure 2. Transient Signal Coded by WTC at 1.0 bps, SNR = 7.1 dB

Figure 3. Test Image (Lenna) of 512 x512

Figure 4. Lenna Coded by DWT-VQ, .5 bpp, SNR=29.5 dB

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